

Study of Financial Performance of Regional Rural Banks

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1. ABSTRACT

Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) were set up as regional based and rural oriented institutions with capital contributed by Government of India, State Government and Sponsor Bank under the Regional Rural Banks Act, 1976. The basic objective of RRBs was to function as professionally managed alternative channel for credit dispensation to small and marginal farmers, agricultural labourers, socio- economically weaker section of population for development of agriculture, trade, commerce, small scale industry and other productive activities in rural areas. RRBs are expected to mobilise resources and deploy the same locally, thus playing a significant role in developing agriculture and rural economy

Keywords: Rural, Government of India, State Government, Rural Area, . performance, RRB, agriculture and rural economy.

2. FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

2.1 Financial Performance

Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. The term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period.

Analysts and investors use financial performance to compare similar firms across the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregate.

2.2 Understanding Financial Performance

There are many stakeholders in a company, including trade creditors, bondholders, investors, employees, and management. Each group has an interest in tracking the financial performance of a company. The financial performance identifies how well a company generates revenues and manages its assets, liabilities, and the financial interests of its stakeholders and stockholders.

3. SOURCES OF DATA COLLECTION

The study is grounded on basis of the Secondary data. The information has been collected from various research works, books, journals, and magazines, Reserve Bank of India annual reports, newspapers, government statistical reports, and websites

The secondary data will be collected from the annual report of the Commercial Banks, Co-operative Banks, Regional Rural Banks, National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development and the Reserve Bank of India, the statistical record of these institutions, various published and unpublished reports, newspapers, journals, books etc.

4. Financial Performance of RRBs

The total credit flow to agriculture, agency-wise, during the last four-year period by all agencies is given below. It may be seen from Table I that the share of RRBs in GLC (Ground level credit) flow to agriculture was 12.1% in 2020-21.

Table I: Ground Level Credit Flow of different agencies (` Crore)

Agency	GLC	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
Cooperatives	Amount	1,50,321	1,52,340	1,57,367	1,90,682
	% Share	12.9	12.1	11.3	12.1
RRBs	Amount	1,41,216	1,49,667	1,65,326	1,90,012
	% Share	12.1	11.9	11.9	12.1
Commercial Banks	Amount	8,71,080	9,54,823	10,70,036	11,94,704
	% Share	74.9	76.0	76.8	75.8
Total		11,62,617	12,56,830	1,392,729	15,75,398

During the year 2020-21, RRBs have achieved 99% of their GLC target.

4.1 Branch Network

As on 31 March 2021, there were 43 RRBs sponsored by 12 commercial banks operating in 26 States (in all states except Sikkim and Goa) and three Union Territories (Jammu & Kashmir, Ladakh and Puducherry). RRBs had a network of 21,856 branches (21,847 branches during previous year) covering 696 districts. 92% of the branches were in the rural areas/semi-urban areas.

4.2 Balance sheet

Catalysed by capital infusion and bolstered by robust growth in borrowings (24.8%) and deposits (9.7%) on the liabilities side, the balance sheet witnessed a healthy growth of 10.8% during FY 2020-21 and stood at Rs. 6.52 lakh crore as on 31 March 2021.

The growth in availability of funds on the liabilities side had a very favourable impact on the growth of credit from the RRBs. The gross loans and advances of the RRBs grew by over 12% during FY 2020-21 in comparison to the average growth rate of 5.3% for all scheduled commercial banks (PSBs-3.2%, Private Sector Banks-8.5%, Foreign Banks- 0.01%).

4.3 Owned Funds

The Owned funds of RRBs, comprising Share Capital and Reserves & Surpluses was ` 38,741 crore as on 31 March 2021 and registered a growth of 11.8 per cent during FY 2020-21. The increase in owned funds has been due to 30 RRBs reporting profit to the tune of ` 3,550 crore and due to increase in share capital on account of recapitalisation.

4.4 Deposits

Deposits, which constitute over 80% of the source of funds of RRBs, grew by 9.7% during the FY 2020-21 and stood at Rs. 5.25 Lakh Crore. As per RBI data, the deposits of banking sector as a whole witnessed a growth of 12.3% during FY 2020-21 and stood at Rs. 154.43 Lakh Crore as on 31 March 2021. The share of low-cost deposits (CASA deposits) marginally improved during the year. The share of CASA deposits of Scheduled Commercial Banks as a whole was 43.7% as on 31 March 2021.

Table II Deposit of RRBs (Rupees in Crore)

S.N	Parameter	31-Mar-19		31-Mar-20		31-Mar-21	
		Amount	Share (%)	Amount	Share (%)	Amount	Share (%)
1	Total Deposits	4,34,444	100	4,78,737	100	5,25,226	100
a)	Current	11,124	3	10,750	2	11,499	2
b)	Savings	2,24,095	51	2,44,414	51	2,71,516	52
c)	Term	1,99,226	46	2,23,573	47	2,42,211	46
2	CASA Deposits (%)	54		53		54	
3	Cost of Deposits (%)	5.0		5.1		4.5	
4	Share in Total Liabilities	80.7		81.4		80.6	

As on 31 March 2021, 22 RRBs had deposit levels higher than ` 10,000 crore and accounted for 80% of the aggregate deposits. 11 RRBs had deposits between ` 5,000 crore and ` 10,000 crore. Thus, 33 RRBs had deposits of more than ` 5,000 crore each, which accounted for 96% of aggregate deposit of all RRBs. While Baroda U.P. Bank had the highest deposit at ` 52,391 crore, Nagaland RB had the lowest deposit size of ` 117 crore.

The share of CASA to total deposits varied between 23% (Saptagiri Grameena Bank) to 79% (Manipur Rural Bank).

Table III: Range of CASA deposits

Range of CASA deposits %	No. of RRBs	% Share of Banks' Deposits in Total Deposits
> 70 %	8	18.1
60 % to 70 %	7	18.6
50 % to 60 %	11	22.7
30 % to 50 %	14	36.1
<30 %	3	4.5
Total	43	100.0

As on 31 March 2021, 8 RRBs viz., Aryavart Bank, Arunachal Pradesh Rural Bank, Assam Gramin Vikash Bank, Chhattisgarh Rajya Gramin Bank, Manipur Rural Bank, Meghalaya Rural Bank, Prathama U.P Gramin Bank and Uttar Bihar Gramin Bank had CASA deposits higher than 70%. 9 RRBs had CASA deposits less than 40 per cent and 8 of them operated in Southern Region of the country.

4.5 Borrowings

Borrowings witnessed a robust growth of 24.8% during the FY 2020-21 and stood at Rs. 67,864 crore as on 31 March 2021. Aided by the Special Liquidity Facility (SLF) and few relaxations in eligibility criteria for availing refinance from NABARD, the borrowings of RRBs from NABARD witnessed a significant growth of 33.5% during FY 2020-21. The share of borrowings from NABARD increased to 91% of the total borrowings of the RRBs as on 31 March 2021.

Table IV: Borrowings of RRBs (Rupees in Crore)

S.N	Parameter	31-Mar-19		31-Mar-20		31-Mar-21	
		Amount	Share (%)	Amount	Share (%)	Amount	Share (%)
1	Total Borrowings	53,548	100	54,393	100	67,864	100
a)	NABARD	46,894	88	46,120	85	61,588	91
b)	Sponsor Bank	3,738	7	4,519	8	3,444	5
c)	Others	2,916	5	3,754	7	2,832	4
2	Borrowings to Liabilities (%)	9.9%		9.2%		10.4%	
3	Borrowings to Loans (%)	19.1%		18.2%		20.3%	
4	Cost of Borrowings (%)	6.0%		5.9%		5.1%	

4.6 Investments

The total investments of RRBs which stood at `2,50,859 crore as on 31 March 2020 increased by 9.9% to `2,75,658 crore as on 31 March 2021. The share of SLR securities in the total investments of RRBs witnessed a sharp increase from 57% to 70% during FY 2020-21. The share of funds deployed in the term deposit accounts has declined from 37 % to 26% during FY 2020-21.

Table V: Investments

(` crore)

S. N	Parameter	31-Mar-19		31-Mar-20		31-Mar-21	
		Amount	Share (%)	Amount	Share (%)	Amount	Share (%)
1	Total Investments	2,26,172	100	2,50,859	100	2,75,658	100
a)	SLR investments	1,38,113	61	1,43,166	57	1,93,097	70
b)	Balances in Deposit Account	72,928	32	92,292	37	72,052	26
c)	Non SLR/Other Investments	15,131	7	15,401	6	10,510	4
2	ID Ratio (%)	52%		52%		52%	
3	SLR Investments to Deposits (%)	32%		30%		37%	
4	Investments to Total Assets	42%		43%		42%	
5	Yield on Investments (%)	7.0%		7.0%		6.5%	

4.7 Loans Outstanding

As per RBI data, Bank Credit of the scheduled commercial banks as a whole grew by 5.3% during the FY 2020-21 to Rs. 110.8 Lakh Crore as on 31 March 2021. The credit growth of RRBs at over 12% was more than double the credit growth of banking sector average.

As on 31 March 2021, of the gross loans & advances of ₹ 3.34 lakh crore, over 90% was towards Priority Sectors identified by RBI. 70% of the loan portfolio of RRBs was towards agriculture sector, followed by MSME (12%), Housing (7%) & Education (1%). As a result of a healthy credit growth during FY 2020-21, the CD ratio of RRBs, as a whole, improved from 62% as on 31 March 2020 to 64% as on 31 March 2021.

Table IV Purpose-wise Outstanding Advances (Rupees in Crore)

Purpose	31 March 2019		31 March 2020		31 March 2021		YoY growth in 2020-21
	Amount	Share (%)	Amount	Share (%)	Amount	Share (%)	
Priority (i to v)	2,55,022	91%	2,70,182	91%	3,00,962	91%	11%
i Agriculture	1,96,228	70%	2,08,762	70%	2,33,145	70%	12%
ii MSME	33,723	12%	35,240	12%	39,543	12%	12%
iii Education	2,634	1%	2,358	1%	2,132	1%	-10%
vi Housing	18,238	6%	19,814	7%	21,127	7%	7%
v Others	4,199	1%	4,008	1%	5,016	1%	25%
Non-priority	25,733	9%	28,032	9%	33,209	9%	18%
Gross Loans O/S	2,80,755	100%	2,98,214	100%	3,34,171	100%	12%
CD Ratio (%)	64.6		62.3		63.6		
Yield on Advances (%)	8.8		9.3		9.2		

4.8 Profitability

After two consecutive years of losses in FY 2018-19 & FY 2019-20, RRBs, as a whole, reported a consolidated net profit of Rs. 1,682 crore during FY 2020-21. RRBs reported consolidated net losses in FY 2018-19, for the first time since FY 1996-97 because of implementation of Regional Rural Bank (Employees') Pension Scheme, 2018 with effect from 1 April 2018 after the verdict of the Hon'ble Supreme Court. Considering huge pension liability on account of implementation of the pension scheme, RBI has permitted RRBs to amortise their total pension liability over a period of five years from 2018-19, subject to a minimum of 20 per cent of the pension liability assessed every year.

During FY 2020-21, 30 RRBs posted profit of ₹ 3,550 crore and 13 RRBs incurred losses of ₹ 1,867 crore. 5 RRBs which incurred losses during FY 2019-20 turned around and posted profits during FY 2020-21. The reasons for improvement in profitability of RRBs during FY 2020-21 are provided below:

- a) Net Interest Margin improved because of greater decline in cost of funds vis-à-vis the decline in yield on assets.
- b) Healthy growth in Miscellaneous Income- RRBs have effectively utilised their high Priority Sector Lending (PSL) portfolio (particularly their agri. & SF/MF portfolio) to augment their Miscellaneous Income. During the FY 2020-21, the total volume of Priority Sector Lending Certificates (PSLCs) traded by RRBs grew by 26% to Rs. 1.92 lakh crore and RRBs accounted for 33% of the total volume of PSLCs traded by all banks. The phased increase in SF/MF targets announced by RBI under PSL guidelines may further help the RRBs in monetising their SF/MF portfolio through issuing PSLCs.
- c) Improvement in Asset Quality and CD ratio. The consolidated income and expenditure statement of RRBs is given in Annexure III. Profitability of RRBs during the last 3 years is summarized in Table No. VII.

Table VII Profitability (Rupees in Crore)

Indicator	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
No. of RRBs	53	45	43
No. in Profit	39	26	30
Profit of RRBs in Profit (Amount)	1,759	2,203	3,550
No. in Loss	14	19	13
Loss of RRBs in Loss (Amount)	2,411	4,411	1,867
No. of RRBs with Accumulated Losses	11	17	17
Accumulated Loss	2,887	6,467	8,264
Aggregate net profit of all RRBs	(-)652	(-)2,208	1,682

4.9 Asset Quality

Consolidated Gross Non-Performing Assets (GNPA) of RRBs has declined in percentage terms from 10.4% to 9.4% during the FY 2020-21. The Net NPA has declined in both absolute and percentage terms during FY 2020-21. The Provision Coverage Ratio (PCR) has shown a continuous improvement over the previous 3 years. 28 RRBs have reported lesser GNPA (%) as on 31 March 2021 vis-a-vis the position as on 31 March 2020. Of these 28 RRBs, 18 RRBs have reported absolute reduction in GNPA (amount). While the substandard assets declined by 7.9% during FY 2020-21, the doubtful and loss assets increased by 4.9 % and 4.8 % respectively.

Table VIII: Status of Non-Performing Asset in RRBs				
(Amount in `crore)				
S. No.	Parameters	31 Mar 2019	31 Mar 2020	31 Mar 2021
Position of NPAs				
1	Gross NPA Amount	30,317	31,106	31,381
2	Net NPA Amount	17,843	16,331	15,094
3	GNPA %	10.8	10.4	9.4
4	Net NPA %	6.8	5.8	4.8
5	Provision Coverage Ratio (%)	40	47	51

Table IX: Classification of Non-Performing Assets							
(Amount in `crore)							
Category of NPA	31-Mar-19		31-Mar-20		31-Mar-21		YoY Growth in 2020-21
	Amount	(%)	Amount	(%)	Amount	(%)	(%)
Sub Standard -1	12,977	4.6	10,608	3.6	9,828	2.9	-7.9
Doubtful Assets -2	16,546	5.9	19,655	6.5	20,666	6.2	4.9
Loss Assets – 3	794	0.3	843	0.3	886	0.3	4.8
Gross NPA (1+2+3)	30,317	10.8	31,106	10.4	31,381	9.4	1.8

Sector-wise status of NPA in RRBs is given in the following Table:

Table X: GNPA (%) across different sectors				
S. No.	Sector / Sub Sector	31 Mar 2019	31 Mar 2020	31 Mar 2021
1	Priority Sector	11.3	10.8	9.9
2	Non-Priority Sector Loans	6.1	6.5	4.6
3	Total NPAs	10.8	10.4	9.4
Sectoral NPA (Priority +Non-Priority)				
I	Agriculture (A+B+C)	9.8	8.7	8.3
A	Farm Credit (i+ii+iii)	9.7	8.5	8.2
i	Crop Loans	9.0	7.3	6.9
ii	Investment Credit	14.9	14.9	18.3
iii	Allied Activities	10.1	11.3	8.5
B	Agriculture Infrastructure	12.2	15.2	15.0
C	Ancillary Activities	30.9	34.1	22.5
II	MSME	20.6	21.4	19.4
III	Education	17.2	26.0	23.1
IV	Housing	7.9	10.0	7.0

The measures taken for reduction in NPAs include the following:

- Review of status of NPAs has been in the agenda of all the meetings conducted by NABARD to review performance of RRBs, in which all the stakeholders including Government of India participate.
- RRBs having *inter alia* Gross NPAs of more than 10% have been identified as ‘RRBs in Focus’ and advised to prepare Monitorable Action Plans to reduce the level of NPA and review the same in the Board meetings.
- Review Meetings of the ‘RRBs in Focus’ are conducted to review the position and take remedial measures
- NABARD has directed all RRBs to compulsorily on-board into the system generated NPAs platform.
- RRBs have informed in the Review Meetings that NPA management cells have been created in RRBs to monitor the recovery and ensure targeted reduction in NPAs.
- At RRB level, all Chairmen with the assistance of their Regional Managers are monitoring branch wise NPA position not only to improve the position, but also to make efforts to contain the growth in NPAs.
- All RRBs on a regular basis organize recovery camps and follow other recovery strategies to reduce the level of NPAs.

4.10 Productivity

The productivity of RRBs, both in terms of business per branch and per employee, has shown steady improvement over the years and stood at ` 39.3 crore and ` 9.8 crore as on 31 March 2021, respectively.

Table XI: Productivity (Amount in ` Crore)

Productivity	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
Per Branch	22.7	24.9	27.9	30.1	32.7	35.6	39.3
Per Employee	5.3	5.9	6.9	7.3	7.7	8.5	9.8

4.11 Credit Deposit Ratio (CD Ratio)

The Credit Deposit Ratio of RRBs stood at 64% as on 31 March 2021 as against 62% as on 31 March 2020. The number of RRBs in different range of CD ratio during the previous 3 years is given in table below. While the Southern and Western states had healthy CD Ratio, the CD Ratio of RRBs in Eastern, North-eastern and Central states was very low.

Table XII: Range of CD ratio				
S. No.	Range of CD Ratio	31 Mar 2019	31 Mar 2020	31 Mar 2021
1	Less than 30%	3	3	3
2	Between 30% to 40%	9	10	7
3	Between 40% to 60%	18	14	14
4	Between 60% to 80%	11	9	10
5	Above 80%	12	9	9
Total		53	45	43

4.12 Capital Adequacy

As per the regulatory stipulations of RBI, RRBs have to maintain a minimum CRAR of 9%. 27 RRBs had CRAR of 9% or more as on 31 March 2021 while 16 RRBs reported CRAR less than 9%. The list of RRBs with CRAR less than 9% is given in Table XVIII. System-wide CRAR of RRBs, marginally declined from 10.3% as on 31 March 2020 to 10.2% as on 31 March 2021.

Table XIII: RRBs with CRAR < 9%		
S. No.	Name of RRB	31.3.2021
1	Vidharbha Konkan Gramin Bank	-20.80
2	Utkal Grameen Bank	-16.01
3	Madhyanchal Gramin Bank	-11.17
4	Ellaquai Dehati Bank	-8.22
5	Odisha Gramya Bank	-7.61
6	Nagaland Rural Bank	-2.93
7	Uttar Bihar Gramin Bank	-2.33
8	J & K Grameen Bank	-0.35
9	Bangiya Gramin Vikash Bank	0.27
10	Paschim Banga Gramin Bank	0.34
11	Assam Gramin Vikash Bank	1.83
12	Manipur Rural Bank	2.37
13	Madhya Pradesh Gramin Bank	2.69
14	Dakshin Bihar Gramin Bank	5.66

Table XIV: RRBs with CRAR < 9%

S. No.	Name of RRB	31.3.2021
15	Uttarakhand Gramin Bank	6.25
16	Kerala Gramin Bank	6.57

4.13 Performance in Government Schemes

Table XV Participation in Government Schemes
As on 31 March 2021, Accounts / Enrolments in Lakh

S.N	Government Scheme	RRBs	Total	Share of RRBs
1	No. of PMJDY Accounts	755.72	4,220	18%
2	No. of Rupay Debit Cards issued to beneficiaries	343.77	3,090	11%
3	Cum. No. of Persons Enrolled under PMSBY	295.22	2,326	13%
4	Cum. No. of Persons Enrolled under PMJJBY	106.87	1,027	10%
5	Cumulative No. of Persons Enrolled under APY	55.22	280	20%
6	Total Number of PM- Kisan Beneficiary-A/cs	179.79	975	18%
7	Kisan Credit Card	129	738	17%

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